

REACTIVE PROCESSING OF SiC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The effect of reactive metals on the pyrolysis of bulk samples of a preceramic polymer was investigated. Research was conducted, primarily, on polycarbosilane and Si metal. X-ray diffraction was used to study the final composition of the composites. Weight loss, shrinkage, density, and final microstructure were studied. The Si addition did not reduce the weight loss, but did reduce the shrinkage. The Si addition improved the crystallinity of the SiC formed. Preliminary studies on using Ti and Mo fillers showed that they reduced both weight loss and shrinkage and tended to produce carbides and silicides.

INTRODUCTION

Processing of ceramic matrix composites is difficult and or expensive, due to problems associated with sintering of the matrix and differential shrinkage between the two phases. High temperature ceramics such as SiC require very high temperatures, elevated pressures, and dopants to improve sintering behavior. The formation of carbides by pyrolysis of a polymeric precursor has been shown to be very useful in the production of ceramic fibers [1]. Attempts to transfer this technique to bulk ceramics has been less promising, because of the high volume shrinkage associated with pyrolysis [2]. This large volume change results in either porous ceramics or very large shrinkage. Low temperature and or low strength secondary phases are also frequently present in the final product, causing a reduction in performance.

One way to improve polymer pyrolysis as a route to bulk ceramic composites, is by the addition of desirable inert fillers and reactive metals [3-5]. Addition of inert fillers reduce the volume fraction of the polymer leading to lower volume change. The reactive metal filler has the potential of reacting with excess carbon in the polymer and producing desired carbides. This reaction can result in a volume expansion that can further reduce the shrinkage of the composite system as shown schematically in Fig. 1.

In this paper, these concepts have been investigated. The polymer used in this study is Polycarbosilane. This is a thermosetting polymer that can be shaped and then cross-linked. Once cross-linked, the thermoset polymer would retain its shape during pyrolysis.

Figure 1: Metal fillers added to polycarbosilane can expand as they form a carbide, making up for the shrinkage of the precursor. (Adapted from Ref.[5])

BACKGROUND

Processing of large, complex shapes by conventional powder processing routes is rather difficult. Typical powder processing of ceramics result in approximately 15% shrinkage. The shrinkage can cause warpage and cracking, so products have to be machined after sintering. This requires diamond abrasives as well as expensive equipment. Other drawbacks to conventional processing is the high temperatures required to sinter carbides.

High Density SiC has been produced from the pyrolysis of organometallic polymers such as polycarbosilane [1]. Pyrolysis does not require as high of temperatures to form SiC, but has a significant amount of shrinkage [2]. This system is widely used for the production of SiC fibers.

Dr. Greil and his co-workers started work on a process that mixes a filler that will react with the excess carbon from the polymer and form a carbide [3-5]. The formation of the carbide can result in a volume expansion. This expansion is then used to make up for the shrinkage of the polymer (Fig.1). Transition metals are used because their carbides are easy to form. This process has been called Active Filler Controlled Pyrolysis (AFCOP) process [4]. Early work by Greil et al. mainly looked at formation of TiC, SiC composites [6-8]. This work shows that the shrinkage can be reduced by the addition of titanium as the active filler, and that TiC and SiC are formed. Other studies have shown that a mixture of polycarbosilane and titanium will produce Ti_5Si_3 and SiC after being pyrolyzed at temperatures ranging from 900°C to 1400°C under Ar [9].

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The polymer that was chosen for the project was polycarbosilane, because of its availability and the understanding of its properties and behavior in making NicalonTM fibers. The polycarbosilane was obtained from Dow Corning. The powder was dissolved in hexane, the hexane was then evaporated off. The resulting residue of polymer was then ground into a fine powder. This powder was then used for making dry pressed samples, roughly of the dimensions 1/2 inch by 1/8 inch. The resulting pellets had very good green strength. The polycarbosilane was dissolved in hexane to ensure uniform mixing of the metal powder. This mixture would then be ground and pressed using the same technique as for the pure polymer samples.

The cross-linking of the pellets turned out to be different then the requirements stated for making fibers. The information received from Dow Corning on the cross-linking of polycarbosilane helped but was not correct for the bulk samples [10,11]. This information recommended that the polycarbosilane should be cross-linked at 190°C in 4 hrs. or less.

This did not produce fully cross-linked samples. It resulted in pellet that were cross-linked on the surface but the middle would be glassy. The center would melt during pyrolysis causing the samples to bloat and rupture. It was concluded that 190°C was too close to the melting point of the polymer and was causing the centers to soften and flow to form the glassy structure that was observed. The glassy center would not allow the oxygen to diffuse into it nearly as fast, so even at very long cross-linking times the center would still not cross-link. To circumvent this problem, cross-linking temperature was reduced. Fully cross-linked samples were obtained by cross-linking in air at 170°C for 48 hours. The cross-linked samples were then pyrolyzed at different temperatures between 1000°C and 1500°C. The weight loss and shrinkage of the samples was measured. In addition, the phase evolution was studied using X-ray diffraction and the microstructure investigated using electron microscopy. Samples with varying amounts of inert (SiC) and reactive metal (primarily Si) fillers in the polymers were next investigated.

RESULTS / DISCUSSION

Bulk samples of polycarbosilane, roughly of the dimensions 1/2 inch by 1/8 inch were dry-pressed. These samples were cross-linked at various temperatures for different lengths of time. The temperature was critical, at too high a temperature, the center of the samples would melt and not cross-link, but at too low of a temperature, the kinetics of cross-linking become very slow.

Figure 2. Weight gain during cross-linking of polycarbosilane

Cross-linking mechanism in polycarbosilane is the incorporation of oxygen to form Si-O-Si cross-linking bonds. The extent of cross-linking was measured based on weight gained during cross-linking due to oxygen incorporation in the samples. The best cross-linking schedule was found to be 170°C for 48 hours. Samples with weight gains above 9% would retain their shape during pyrolysis, but the cross-linking is not complete as can be seen from Fig 2. The amount of oxygen incorporated is important because it affects the weight loss, shrinkage and phase evolution during pyrolysis. In order to make comparable samples, all cross-linking was done at 170°C for 48 hours. As can be seen from Fig. 2, for this schedule, the weight gain is about 13%.

The cross-linked samples were pyrolyzed between 1000°C and 1500°C for 4 hours in Ar. The weight losses for the pure PCS and the samples with a reactive metal addition are presented in Fig. 3. The weight loss for samples below 1300°C was 18% and increased with temperature to more than 22% for 1500°C. The weight loss below 1300°C is due to

the loss of hydrocarbons during the degradation of the PCS. This loss does not change until temperatures above 1300°C where SiO evolution starts. Samples mixed with Si behaved similarly but with an additional weight loss at temperatures above 1300°C due to the loss of added Si metal. Since weight loss does not change at low temperatures we conclude that the Si does not react with C that is given off during the degradation of PCS. The increased weight loss above 1300°C is attributed to the Si metal being evolved (as SiO). The SiO evolution was confirmed by the X-ray diffraction of deposits taken from inside the furnace tube.

Figure 3. The normalized weight loss.

The linear shrinkage was measured for each sample, and is shown in Fig. 4 as a function of pyrolysis temperature. Linear shrinkage for pure PCS was about 26%. The addition of Si metal greatly reduced the shrinkage, 10% Si by volume had a shrinkage of 16%, 15% Si by volume had a shrinkage of 12.5%, and the 20% Si by volume had a shrinkage of 11.2%. The addition of Si metal constrained the matrix reducing the shrinkage and

Figure 4. Linear Shrinkage for each filler system.

increasing the porosity (as will be shown later). The samples with 50% SiC by volume had a shrinkage of 1.6%, along with less porosity than the Si filled samples. The Si containing samples were found to have very high porosity. The measured bulk densities for the samples after pyrolysis are shown in Fig. 5 as a function of pyrolysis temperature. The bulk samples of pure PCS achieved densities of 90% that of Nicalon® fibers, with a

maximum in density of 2.36 g/cm^3 at 1300°C . The addition of Si metal reduced the density to 1.6 g/cm^3 for the samples run at 1300°C and lower. The samples run at 1500°C had a density of 1.1 g/cm^3 . The 50% SiC by volume samples had a maximum density of 2.07 g/cm^3 at 1300°C , and a minimum of 1.95 g/cm^3 at 1500°C .

Figure 5. Density comparisons for samples forming SiC after pyrolysis.

Phase evolution was studied using x-ray diffraction. The pure PCS formed SiC during pyrolysis, but at the temperatures investigated, the SiC was either amorphous or nanocrystalline. This is shown in Fig. 6 as low intensities, broad peaks at low temperatures. The peaks become sharper and more intense as the crystallinity of the sample increases. The crystallinity does not start to improve until after 1300°C , but even at 1500°C the peaks are quite broad with very low intensity and secondary peaks are not present.

Figure 6. Crystalline SiC evolution.

The formation of crystalline SiC during pyrolysis is significantly improved by the addition of Si is shown in Fig 7 for samples heated treated at 1500°C . The 10% Si addition improved the crystallinity of the SiC, but not to the extent of the 15% or 20% Si additions. The peaks become very sharp and intense at the higher metal content. There is also no other crystalline phases detected. This suggests that there is no Si left in the sample after being heated to 1500°C which agrees with the findings of SiO evolution

consuming Si above 1300°C. The 15% and 20% Si samples had the same affect on improving the crystallinity, But the 10% Si sample has peaks with much lower intensity. This suggest that there is a critical amount of Si needed to improve crystallinity.

Figure 7. X-Ray Diffraction data showing that the addition of Si improves the crystallinity of the SiC formed at 1500°C

The use of titanium and molybdenum as reactive fillers is also being investigated. The preliminary findings have shown promise in both systems. Both the Ti and Mo samples had lower weight loss than the PCS at 1100°C showing that these metals do capture carbon during the degradation of the PCS. The Ti sample showed no further weight loss due to the evolution of other species. The Mo sample has a larger weight loss at 1300°C than the Si containing samples, but at 1500°C the weight loss was lower. The linear shrinkage was reduced by the addition of Ti and Mo. For comparison the linear shrinkage for pure PCS was about 26%. 15% Ti by volume reduced the shrinkage to 21% whereas the 15% Mo reduced shrinkage to 13%. The pure PCS and Ti samples had the lowest porosity as observed by optical and electron microscopy. The preliminary X-ray analysis of the Ti and Mo samples showed that they tend to form both carbides and silicides, but the formation of SiC was not detected on the diffraction patterns. The major phase formed during pyrolysis of the Ti samples was TiC. The peaks for SiC formed from PCS and the TiC peaks overlap making positive identification of the phases difficult. The Mo samples formed MoC at low temperatures and molybdenum silicides at the higher temperatures. Molybdenum metal is still present at 1100°C, but at 1300°C it is consumed to form silicides. The MoC is consumed above 1300°C so there is only a trace of MoC and no Mo at 1500°C.

CONCLUSIONS

Pre-ceramic polymer samples could be dry-pressed, cross-linked and pyrolyzed to form SiC. Cross-linking schedule for bulk PCS was optimized at 170°C for 48 hours in air. The pure PCS was found to evolve SiO at temperatures at and above 1300°C. This increased the weight loss, but the shrinkage remained constant at 26%. A maximum density of 2.4 g/cm³ was achieved at 1300°C, which is greater than 90% of the density of Nicalon® fibers. The addition of reactive metals was found to reduce the shrinkage. Si was found not to react with C being given off during the degradation of the PCS. Excess Si forms volatile SiO at higher temperatures resulting in increased weight loss. The Si addition constrained the matrix reducing the shrinkage, but resulted in higher porosity.

The most significant finding is the addition of Si was found to aid in the formation of crystalline SiC. This was observed at pyrolysis temperatures above 1300°C and for all the volume fractions of Si investigated. The addition of SiC to the 15% Si system produced samples that have a linear shrinkage of 1.6%, but still have a large amount of porosity. Samples with such high solids loading have contact between the particles in the green state. The preliminary results from the Ti and Mo samples are encouraging. The formation of carbides was achieved, and the shrinkage was reduced.

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